

From The Desk of Guest Editor....

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Poor oral health is potential to affect the overall general health either directly or indirectly. This gave the concept of 'ORAL SEPSIS' long time back (Miller & Hunter, 1896). Subsequently, the concept of 'FOCAL INFECTION' (Billings, 1912) came to an existence. The "focal infection theory" is a historical concept theorizing that oral infection may act as a source of infection (focus of infection) and can infect distant parts of the body. Later on, it was observed that extraction of teeth did not necessarily make an ill person better, people with no obvious oral infection also develop systemic diseases and edentulous patients with no oral infection develops systemic diseases. Considering these facts, the concept of Focal Infection came to an end around 1940. Based on the progresses made in understanding of pathogenic mechanisms and of molecular biology, the "focal infection theory" finds new interest in medical field and this concept has revisited in late eighties, though it is still unproven and speculative only.

Periodontitis is the most prevalent condition of oral cavity. It is caused predominantly by Gram-negative, anaerobic, microaerophilic bacteria that colonise the subgingival area, and is modified by environmental and stress-related behavioural factors. It is the most evident example of 'focal infection' phenomenon today: in fact, bacteria are able to migrate, develop and cause health issues at distant sites. In a wide range of literatures, a link between periodontitis and systemic diseases is suggested. The systemic diseases include cardiovascular disease, diabetes, adverse pregnancy outcomes, respiratory tract infection, musculoskeletal diseases, gastrointestinal and colorectal cancer, Alzheimer's disease, etc.,. A cause-and-effect relationship has not been established yet. Periodontal pathogens and their metabolic by-products present in the mouth may modulate the immune response beyond the oral cavity, thus promoting the development of systemic conditions. Transient bacteremia, microbial toxins and metastatic inflammation caused by immunological injury induced by oral microorganisms are regarded as the possible mechanisms or pathways linking oral infections to secondary systemic effect. Elevated levels of inflammatory factors (C-reactive protein, interleukin-6, and neutrophils) serve as predictors of cardiovascular events and disease. Some of the oral bacteria are known to be

associated with platelet aggregation, which is an important event, for thrombosis that indicates the association of, periodontitis, with myocardial infarction. A remarkable similarity exists, in the pathogenesis of periodontal diseases and rheumatoid arthritis.

Again, some of the systemic conditions may in turn increase the incidence and severity of periodontal disease by modifying the body's immune response to periodontal bacteria and their by-products. It also appears that interventional periodontal care remains invaluable not only for oral health but also for general health. Thus, evidence suggests a bi-directional relationship between periodontitis and systemic diseases.

For many years, the dental profession has recognized the effects of systemic conditions on the oral cavity. In contrast, now-a-days dental professions are beginning to understand more fully the impact of the periodontal disease on systemic health. Thus, a greater integration of medicine and dentistry representing more responsibility of a dental surgeon in the management of their patients' systemic health and similarly, the physicians active role in their patients' oral health is developing.

The observations made by various researchers suggest that medical specialists must recognize the emerging and increasing significance of potential negative effects of periodontal infections on systemic health. If comprehensive health care is ever to be achieved, oral health should not be seen as a separate, distant, and unrelated to life, span. Similarly, Dental Surgeons must improve their knowledge and clinical exposure of relevant systemic conditions in order to interact and relate meaningfully with their medical colleagues. This is the goal of "Periodontal Medicine," which encourages effective team approach in clinical practice and inspires upgradation of strong cooperation between Dental and Medical professionals in patient management from systemic point of view rather than concentrate in and around their own fields, without which it is impossible to manage these kinds of diseases effectively. The emerging field of Periodontal Medicine offers new insights into the concept of the oral cavity as one system interconnected with the whole human body. However, we, the Dental Surgeon, should remember that periodontitis may increase the risk for many systemic disorders, not the exclusive cause of such disorders.

Since periodontal diseases are preventable and manageable and the treatment is also unhazardous, it might represent an important modifiable risk factor for systemic diseases and this will help further in reduction of the social burden globally. In the light of current knowledge, regular dental checkup is strongly advocated.

I put down my pen for this editorial with an appeal to all my fellow colleagues of Dental and Medical fraternity that it is the time to move from RESEARCH TO PRACTICE.

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